

DEVELOPMENT ISSUES OF VIRTUAL READING

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Abstract

This article describes the theoretical aspects of virtual reading, its role in people's lives today and the impact of social networks, as well as the existing opportunities in this area, the analysis of the attitude of civil servants and educators to virtual reading.

Keywords: virtual, reading, virtual world, social network, information security, information technology, globalization, bibliobus, internet, culture.

Introduction

In today's globalized world, where information and communication technologies are widely introduced and, as a result, the virtual world is gaining popularity, the culture of virtual reading is becoming one of the most pressing topics.

This topic has already created virtual reality - beyond the boundaries of the field of cybernetics, has penetrated deeply into the system of social sciences and humanities, and has become the main object of study in the field of socio-philosophy, psychology and philosophy of culture.

In general, today, universities and research centers in some developed countries pay great attention to the scientific study and research on the issues of virtual culture that are emerging in modern societies.

In particular, scientists working in the social sciences and humanities, and the exact sciences are conducting research on the virtual world.

Western scientists Castells, M. McLuhan, E. Toffler and N. Moiseev[4] also conducted scientific research on the impact of the virtual world on the formation of society.

Philosophical conceptual views on the effective use of the culture of reading and the possibilities of virtual reality have been developed by M. Bekmurodov, A.G. Muminov, S. Otamurodov and other scientists.[1]

The analysis of the studied literature in the field of socio-humanitarian, philosophical and information technologies shows that the role of social networks in the formation of a culture of virtual reading should be considered as a separate holistic topic.

The reason is the need to develop skills such as the ability to obtain the necessary, important information from the endless streams of information, to search for information of interest in all types of information materials.

Methods

Theoretical aspects of virtual reading, its role in people's lives today and the impact of social networks and the opportunities available in this regard, the study and research of attitudes of civil servants and educators to virtual reading, analysis of relevant literature and sources, analysis of legal documents, social survey .

In particular, in order to study the theoretical foundations of the subject, the literature in the field of socio-humanitarian, philosophical and information technologies was studied. In doing so, the views of Western and local scholars were analyzed.

For example, the research of M. Castells[2], one of the founders of the information society, reflects the socio-philosophical aspect of the nature of virtualization, which describes the concept of virtual reality as a phenomenon that easily transcends the boundaries of time and space such a "virtual reality network" would have a strong impact on all other aspects of social life, especially the

spiritual and moral world of young people.

The concept of reading culture is noted and given a special description in the textbook "History, Theory and Methodology of Social and Cultural Activity" co-authored by M. Bekmurodov, A. Umarov, U. Qoraboev, Z. Haydarovs. "A culture of reading requires an interest in books, an incentive for people to become more familiar with the literature, as well as the skills and competencies to make full use of the sources of information".[1]

It is the issue of reading in recent years in our country at the level of state policy. "We need to attract investment in our country not only in the economy, but also in the field of scientific know-how".[6]

In particular, on March 19, 2020 under the chairmanship of President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to pay more attention to youth, attract the younger generation to culture, arts, physical culture and sports, develop their skills in using information technology, promote reading among young people, ensure women's employment "The more spiritually mature young people are, the stronger their immunity against various disorders," the head of the state said in a video conference. At the end of the meeting, the head of our state put forward 5 important initiatives to establish work in the social, spiritual and educational spheres on the basis of a new system. The third of these initiatives is aimed at organizing the effective use of computer technology and the Internet among the population and youth, while the fourth initiative is aimed at raising the morale of young people, the organization of systematic work to promote reading among them.

The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-4354 of June 7, 2019 "On further improvement of information library services to the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan" also pays special attention to the development of electronic digital libraries. In particular, the resolution provides

for the development and approval of a program for the development of public-private partnership in the field of information library, private and digital (virtual) libraries in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019-2024.[3]

Based on the reforms above, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Information and Library Activities" dated April 13, 2011 was amended and supplemented in 2018, 2020 and 2021. In particular, in 2021, changes and additions were made to 17 articles of the law.

From the above, it is clear that in our country, serious attention is paid to the issue of reading, especially virtual (electronic) reading.

The concept of "virtual" on the Internet is defined as follows. "Virtuality" is an imaginary object that does not really exist, but can occur under certain conditions.

According to the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, edited by A. Madvaliev, the word "mutolaa" - (Arabic) means to read carefully, to study, and, unlike ordinary reading, means to read and study carefully.[5]

In general, the social sciences and humanities (philosophy, sociology, psychology, political science, cultural studies, literature and philology), as well as exact and technical sciences (information technology and computer science, information security, digital technologies and artificial intelligence) are engaged in this issue.

For this reason, in the study of this study, the methods of studying the theories of scientists, the analysis of regulatory documents were used.

However, the research focuses on empirical sociological research. This is because the data obtained by this method cannot be found in other sources.

The main method used in the study is the "Survey" method. In order to collect effective data among a large number of individuals and to be able to accurately compare the answers of the respondents, a survey of respondents was

organized through a questionnaire form.

Results

In the process of reforms and globalization in the field, one of the important tasks is to study and analyze the views of the population on virtual reading.

For this reason, a survey was conducted among civil servants and educators to find out their views on virtual reading. The questionnaire consisted of 6 closed questions and was conducted in groups of civil servants and educators on the social network "telegram.org". A total of 235 respondents took part in the survey. The majority of respondents (39%) reported that 50-70% of their daily reading was virtual (electronic) reading. 26%, 22% and 13% of respondents reported reading 30-50%, 10-30% and 70-90% virtually (electronically) respectively.

When asked how many hours a day they spend on virtual reading, 31 percent

of respondents said it was 3-4 hours. (Figure 1)

Figure 1.

When respondents were asked which sources they mainly read virtually, it was found that the vast majority of them, more precisely 71 percent, read on

social networks. (Figure 2)

Figure 2

The virtual reading of the vast majority of respondents, including civil servants and teachers, consisted of socio-political and legal news, accounting for

78 per cent. (Figure 3)

Figure 3

Discussion

Participants were also asked about the pros and cons of virtual reading during the survey.

Indicate the positive aspects of virtual reading		Indicate the disadvantages of virtual reading	
Saves distance, time and money	73%	Adversely affects health (eyes)	79%
You can read at any time and place	67%	Sometimes the need for the internet	65%

		and power supply	
Easy to quick search necessary information	60%	Not feeling aesthetic pleasure	60%
Quickly and easily (via link) access to or find the source (literature) used in e-books	37%	Forms laziness of reader about reading	30%
Availability of thousands of volumes of books in a portable device	27%	Distraction from the main goal due to the large amount of data flow	22%
Other	10%	Other	11%

As can be seen from the table above, the main advantage of virtual reading over traditional reading is that it has the ability to read data at any time through a portable gadget (electronic device).

However, in addition to the advantages above, there are also drawbacks, which are acknowledged by the respondents. In particular, reading through gadgets is seen as a major health risk and a lack of information security.

It is clear that the culture of virtual reading through a special mobile (book) application, a special site and platforms is not sufficiently formed. This can also be explained by the fact that the scale of fiction and textbooks in the daily virtual reading of Internet users is insufficient. (Figure 2)

Conclusions

At a time when the socio-economic and political-cultural landscape of the world is changing day by day, man and his maturity are very important issues. In particular, improving the quality of human capital is seen as one of the most important tools in the fight against poverty. The world's leading nations have mastered the formation of knowledge, skills and their use. (K., 2021)[7] Of course, the role and influence of reading, especially virtual reading, on the formation of human capital is great.

In conclusion, the effective use of modern virtual technologies in the global

information society is becoming increasingly important. The reason is that the role of virtual reading in the formation of human capital and intellectual property is growing.

The next discoveries and reforms to be made in the field can be divided into 2 areas:

The first is the area of reducing the negative impact of electronic devices (computers, phones, tablets and gadgets) on human health (especially radiation).

The second is the area of information security in the virtual world in the era of globalization.

Most readers prefer virtual reading to paper books for a number of reasons. In particular, the fact that 50-70% of the daily reading of the majority of civil servants and educators, the most active and intellectually gifted part of society, is virtual reading, shows how important it is to form a culture of virtual reading.

References

1. Bekmurodov M., Umarov A., Qoraboev U., Haydarov Z. History, theory and methodology of socio-cultural activity. - Tashkent: Ma'naviyat, 2016. - 335 p.
2. Castells M. Formation of a society of network structures// New post-industrial wave in the West: Anthology - M.: Academia, 1999. - p. 494.
3. <https://lex.uz/docs/4372449>
4. McLuhan M. Understanding Media: The Extensions of Man. M. : CANON-Press-C. 2003.
5. Madvaliev A. Annotated dictionary of the Uzbek language. Edited by National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, 2016. 655 p.
6. Mirziyoev, Shavkat Miromonovich. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, NMIU, 2019. - 88 p.

7. Uzakov K. Issues of employment in poverty reduction. - Academic Research in Educational Sciences, Volume 2, Issue 10, 2021. – P. 579-594. //DOI: 10.24412/2181-1385-2021-10-579